

Supplementary data

1 Supplementary Table S1. Comparison of the accumulation of MIB (a) and GSM (b) between rainbow
2 trout and European whitefish. Lipid percentage was used as a covariant (0.90 correlation expectancy),
3 but it showed no statistical significance (p=0.60 and p=0.80, respectively). The value p=0.998 for
4 MIB indicated no difference between the species. For GSM, slopes differed somewhat but no
5 statistically significant difference was found (p=0.15).

6 a)

Parameter estimates for MIB (1000 Imputations)							
Parameter	Species	Estimate	Std. Error	95% Confidence Limits		T value	P value
Intercept		-0.2654	0.2686	-0.7918	0.2610	-0.99	0.323
Species	Rainbow trout	0.0611	0.3515	-0.6278	0.7500	0.17	0.862
Species	European whitefish	0
Days		0.0095	0.0033	0.0031	0.0159	2.91	0.004
Days*Species	Rainbow trout	0	0.0025	-0.0048	0.0048	0	0.998
Days*Species	European whitefish	0
Lipid content		0.0314	0.0601	-0.0864	0.1492	0.52	0.601

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8 b)

Parameter estimates for GSM (1000 Imputations)							
Parameter	Species	Estimate	Std. Error	95% Confidence Limits		T value	P value
Intercept		-0.2410	0.3224	-0.8730	0.3908	-0.75	0.455
Species	Rainbow trout	0.0407	0.3883	-0.7203	0.8017	0.10	0.917
Species	European whitefish	0
Days		0.0112	0.0032	0.0049	0.0175	3.49	0.001
Days*Species	Rainbow trout	0.0038	0.0026	-0.0013	0.0089	1.45	0.146
Days*Species	European whitefish	0
Lipid content		-0.0151	0.0597	-0.1322	0.1021	-0.25	0.801

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